

**POSITIVE INTEGERS REPRESENTED BY REGULAR
PRIMITIVE POSITIVE-DEFINITE INTEGRAL TERNARY
QUADRATIC FORMS**

Greg Doyle

*Centre for Research in Algebra and Number Theory, School of Mathematics and
Statistics, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada*

gregorydoyle@hotmail.com

Joseph B. Muskat

Department of Computer Science, Bar Ilan University, Ramat Gan, Israel

muskat@cs.biu.ac.il

Lerna Pehlivan

*Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science, University
of Twente, Enschede, Netherlands*

l.pehlivan@utwente.nl

Kenneth S. Williams¹

*Centre for Research in Algebra and Number Theory, School of Mathematics and
Statistics, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada*

kennethwilliams@cunet.carleton.ca

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Abstract

In 1997 Jagy, Kaplansky and Schiemann determined that there are at most 913 (classes of) primitive, positive-definite, integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dxy + exz + fxy$ which are regular. In this paper the positive integers represented by these 913 ternary forms are given.

1. Introduction

In this paper we are concerned with ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dxy + exz + fxy$ that are primitive, positive-definite and integral. Such a form g is called regular if for each positive integer n the solvability of the congruence $g(x, y, z) \equiv n \pmod{m}$ for every positive integer m implies the solvability of $g(x, y, z) = n$ in integers x, y and z [10]. It is known from the work of Dickson and Jones that if

¹corresponding author

$g(x, y, z)$ is regular then there are a finite number of progressions $\{A^k(Bl+C)|k, l = 0, 1, \dots\}$, where A, B and C are positive integers, such that a positive integer n is represented by g if and only if n does not belong to any of these progressions. They are called the progressions corresponding to the regular form g [11] - [14]. These progressions are of the forms

(1) $2^k(8l+C)$ ($l = 0, 1, 2, \dots$), where k runs through some of the integers in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and $C \in \{1, 3, 5, 7\}$,

and

(2) $p^k(pl+C)$ ($l = 0, 1, 2, \dots$), where p is an odd prime dividing $4abc + def - ad^2 - be^2 - cf^2$, k runs through some of the integers in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and C ranges through some of the integers in $\{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$, see [13, Theorem 5, p. 123].

The classical result of this type is the theorem of Legendre: the positive integer n is represented by $x^2 + y^2 + z^2$ if and only if $n \neq 4^k(8l+7)$ for any non-negative integers k and l [1, 15]. The study of regular forms was started by Dickson [5]. Jones [11] determined in 1928 that there are precisely 102 diagonal regular forms, see also [14]. These can be found listed in Dickson's book [6] together with their corresponding progressions. In 1997 Jagy, Kaplansky and Schiemann [10] found that there are at most 913 regular forms, but for 22 of them regularity was not established. These are the forms in lines numbered 226, 384, 469, 489, 559, 578, 609 in Table 1 and lines numbered 787, 800, 813, 839, 857, 858, 872, 878, 884, 890, 895, 896, 907, 909, 913 in Table 2. The authors indicated that a followup paper presenting detailed proofs and descriptions of the computations was planned but, as far as the authors of this paper can determine, it never appeared. More recently, eight of these (numbers 384, 469, 489, 559, 578, 609, 858 and 895) were proved to be regular by Oh [16]. The remaining fourteen forms were proved to be regular under the assumption of the Generalized Riemann Hypothesis for certain L -functions by Oliver [17]. These forms are marked in Tables 1 and 2 with an asterisk. Table 3 gives references for those regular ternary quadratic forms whose progressions have been given in the literature.

The table of the 102 diagonal regular forms together with their corresponding progressions is perhaps one of the most useful tables in the theory of ternary quadratic forms. It is the purpose of this paper to extend the Dickson-Jones table from diagonal ternary regular forms to all regular ternary forms, see Tables 1 and 2. Ours is a numerical study based on the assumption that all the 913 ternary forms given by Jagy, Kaplansky and Schiemann are in fact regular, and so their corresponding progressions are as in (1) and (2). Tables 1, 2 and 3 are located in the Appendix at the end of this paper.

2. Tables 1 and 2

We let $\mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbb{N}_0$ denote the sets of integers, positive integers and nonnegative integers respectively. The ternary $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$ is said to be even if d, e and f are all even and odd if at least one of d, e and f is odd. Table 1 relates to even ternaries and Table 2 to odd ternaries. The discriminant of an even positive-definite ternary quadratic form $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$ used in this paper is the positive integer given by

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & f/2 & e/2 \\ f/2 & b & d/2 \\ e/2 & d/2 & c \end{vmatrix} = abc + \frac{1}{4}(def - (ad^2 + be^2 + cf^2))$$

and that of an odd ternary form is

$$4 \begin{vmatrix} a & f/2 & e/2 \\ f/2 & b & d/2 \\ e/2 & d/2 & c \end{vmatrix} = 4abc + def - ad^2 - be^2 - cf^2.$$

Throughout the tables, k and l denote non-negative integers unless otherwise specified. In particular in expressions such as $25l - 5$ (which occurs for form number 8) the integer l is understood to be a positive integer.

We have presented the progressions corresponding to the same prime in such a way that they do not overlap. For example in [6] the progressions corresponding to the ternary form $x^2 + 16y^2 + 16z^2$, which is number 237 in Table 1, are given as $4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$. However

$$\{4l + 3 | l \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \cap \{4^k(8l + 7) | k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0\} = \{8l + 7 | l \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

and

$$\{16l + 12 | l \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \cap \{4^k(8l + 7) | k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0\} = \{32l + 28 | l \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

so we prefer to list the progressions equivalently as

$$4l + 2, 8l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$$

or with our convention that $l \in \mathbb{N}$ for the progression $8l - 3$ as

$$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7).$$

None of these progressions overlap.

We conclude this introduction by describing how the calculation of the progressions in Tables 1 and 2 (see Appendix) were performed. Three of the coauthors of this paper calculated independently the progressions (1) and (2) of each of the 913 ternaries given in [10] by slight variations of the algorithm which we now describe.

For each form $F = ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$ in the table of Jagy, Kaplansky and Schiemann, it was checked for n from 1 to N (usually $= 10^5$) whether n is represented by F or not using the result that if n is represented by F then there is a representation (x, y, z) satisfying $|x| \leq \left\lfloor \sqrt{\frac{(4bc-d^2)n}{M}} \right\rfloor$, $|y| \leq \left\lfloor \sqrt{\frac{(4ac-e^2)n}{M}} \right\rfloor$, $|z| \leq \left\lfloor \sqrt{\frac{(4ab-f^2)n}{M}} \right\rfloor$, where $M = 4abc + def - ad^2 - be^2 - cf^2$, see [18]. This information was stored in a boolean vector R (the representation vector) of length N . The vector's n th component has the value TRUE if n is represented by the form F and value FALSE otherwise. For each form F the odd primes dividing M were found and the progression candidates determined as in (1) and (2). A table of these possible progression candidates was constructed. The algorithm iterated over all n from 1 to N for which R_n is TRUE. In each step all progression candidates with n in their progression were eliminated. At the conclusion of the algorithm the set of all integers up to N which appear in any of the remaining progression candidates were identified. Using the representation vector R all numbers in this set were verified not to be represented by F . Finally the complement set of integers, that is, all integers from 1 to N which do not appear in any of the remaining progression candidates, were verified to be represented by F using the representation vector. If both verifications were successful we marked the set of progression candidates as valid progressions corresponding to F .

One author checked the progressions up to $N = 102400$ and another checked them up to $N = 10^6$ for those forms F for which $4abc + def - ad^2 - be^2 - cf^2$ has a prime factor $p \geq 13$ as well as for the 22 forms not yet proved regular. All four authors checked Tables 1 and 2 against the computer output to eliminate typos.

3. Location of Results

We have found in the literature explicit progressions for 121 of the 913 ternaries listed in the Jagy-Kaplansky-Schiemann table [10] (see Appendix). This includes the 102 diagonal regular ternaries given by Dickson in [6, pp. 112 - 113]. References are given in Table 3. The progressions for these 121 ternaries are in agreement with the progressions in Tables 1 and 2 although they may be given in a slightly different form.

4. Proofs

In this section we give the proofs for a few of the results in Tables 1 and 2, and in doing so we illustrate a variety of different approaches. The proofs of numbers 41,

53 and 55 appear to be new.

Proof of no. 6. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3$ be a solution of $n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2$. Then

$$(x, y, z) \equiv \begin{cases} (0, 0, 0) \pmod{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \\ (0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 0) \text{ or } (1, 0, 0) \pmod{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ (0, 1, 1), (1, 0, 1) \text{ or } (1, 1, 0) \pmod{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \\ (1, 1, 1) \pmod{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Thus when $n \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}$ all of the solutions of $n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2$ satisfy $y \equiv z \pmod{2}$, whereas if $n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ exactly one third of the solutions satisfy $y \equiv z \pmod{2}$. The mapping $\lambda : \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2, y \equiv z \pmod{2}\} \rightarrow \{(u, v, w) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = u^2 + 2v^2 + 2w^2\}$ given by

$$\lambda((x, y, z)) = \left(x, \frac{y+z}{2}, \frac{y-z}{2}\right)$$

is a bijection. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2, y \equiv z \pmod{2}\} \\ = \text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + 2y^2 + 2z^2\} \end{aligned}$$

and so

$$\text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + 2y^2 + 2z^2\} = \alpha \text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2\},$$

where

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}, \\ \frac{1}{3} & \text{if } n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Finally

$$\begin{aligned} n \text{ is not represented by } x^2 + 2y^2 + 2z^2 \\ \iff \text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + 2y^2 + 2z^2\} = 0 \\ \iff \text{card}\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}^3 | n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2\} = 0 \\ \iff n \text{ is not represented by } x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \\ \iff n = 4^k(8l + 7) \text{ for some } k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0, \end{aligned}$$

by Legendre's theorem. □

Proof of no. 25. Suppose first that the positive integer n is represented by $x^2 + 4y^2 + 4z^2 + 4yz$. Hence there exist integers r, s and t such that

$$n = r^2 + 4s^2 + 4t^2 + 4st.$$

Clearly $n \equiv r^2 \pmod{4}$ so $n \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$, that is $n \neq 4l + 2, 4l + 3$. Further n is represented by $x^2 + y^2 + 3z^2$ with $x = r, y = 2s + t$ and $z = t$. Thus, as $x^2 + y^2 + 3z^2$ is regular by [6, p. 112] we have $n \neq 9^k(9l + 6)$. Conversely suppose that $n \neq 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$. Then, as $n \neq 9^k(9l + 6)$ by the regularity of $x^2 + y^2 + 3z^2$ we have

$$n = u^2 + v^2 + 3w^2$$

for some integers u, v and w . As $n \neq 4l + 2, 4l + 3$ we deduce that $(u^2, v^2, w^2) \equiv (0, 0, 0), (0, 1, 0), (0, 1, 1), (1, 0, 0), (1, 0, 1)$ or $(1, 1, 1) \pmod{4}$. Thus either $u \equiv v \pmod{2}$ or $v \equiv w \pmod{2}$. Interchanging u and v if necessary we may suppose that $v \equiv w \pmod{2}$. Then n is represented by $x^2 + 4y^2 + 4z^2 + 4yz$ with

$$x = u, y = w, z = \frac{v - w}{2}.$$

We have proved that n is represented by $x^2 + 4y^2 + 4z^2 + 4yz$ if and only if $n \neq 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$. $\square$

Proof of no. 41. By [10, Table 2] $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$ is regular. Its discriminant is $20 = 2^2 \cdot 5$. By (1) and (2) the progressions corresponding to $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$ are among

$$2^k(8l + r) \quad (k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0, r = 1, 3, 5, 7)$$

and

$$5^k(5l + r) \quad (k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0, r = 1, 2, 3, 4).$$

The following integers are represented by $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$:

$$\begin{array}{lll} 2^{2k} \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}) & x = 0, & y = 0, \quad z = 2^{k-1}, \\ 2^{2k+1} \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 2^k, & y = 0, \quad z = 0, \\ 2^{2k} \cdot 3 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 0, & y = 2^k, \quad z = 0, \\ 2^{2k+1} \cdot 3 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 2^k, & y = 0, \quad z = 2^k, \\ 2^{2k} \cdot 13 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}) & x = 0, & y = 2^{k+1}, \quad z = 2^{k-1}, \\ 2^{2k+1} \cdot 13 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 2^k, & y = -2^{k+1}, \quad z = 2^{k+1}, \\ 2^{2k} \cdot 7 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 0, & y = -2^k, \quad z = 2^k, \\ 2^{2k+1} \cdot 7 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 2^k, & y = -2^{k+1}, \quad z = 2^k, \\ 5^{2k} \cdot 6 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 5^k, & y = 0, \quad z = 5^k, \\ 5^{2k} \cdot 2 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 5^k, & y = 0, \quad z = 0, \\ 5^{2k+1} \cdot 2 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 5^k, & y = -2 \cdot 5^k, \quad z = 0, \\ 5^{2k} \cdot 3 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 0, & y = 5^k, \quad z = 0, \\ 5^{2k+1} \cdot 3 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 3 \cdot 5^k, & y = -5^k, \quad z = 0, \\ 5^{2k} \cdot 4 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}_0) & x = 0, & y = 0, \quad z = 5^k. \end{array}$$

Thus

$$2^k(8l + 1) (k \in \mathbb{N}), \quad 2^k(8l + 3) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0), 2^k(8l + 5) (k \in \mathbb{N}), \quad 2^k(8l + 7) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0),$$

$$5^{2k}(5l + 1) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0), 5^k(5l + 2) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0), 5^k(5l + 3) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0), 5^{2k}(5l + 4) (k \in \mathbb{N}_0),$$

are not among the progressions associated with $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$. This leaves

$$8l + 1, 8l + 5, 5^{2k+1}(5l + 1), 5^{2k+1}(5l + 4)$$

to examine. We have

$$2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy \equiv \begin{cases} 0 \pmod{4} & \text{if } (x, y) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{2}, \\ 2 \pmod{4} & \text{if } (x, y) \equiv (1, 0) \pmod{2}, \\ 3 \pmod{4} & \text{if } y \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Hence positive integers $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ are not represented by $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$.

Now suppose that $n = 5^{2k+1}(5l + r)$ ($r = 1, 4$) is represented by $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$. Then there exist integers a, b and c such that

$$2a^2 + 3b^2 + 4c^2 + 2ab = n,$$

so that setting $d_0 = 2a + b, b_0 = b, c_0 = c$ we have

$$d_0^2 + 5b_0^2 + 8c_0^2 = 2 \cdot 5^{2k+1}(5l + r).$$

Thus $5|d_0^2 + 3c_0^2$ and so $5|d_0$ and $5|c_0$. If $k \geq 1$ we deduce $25|5b_0^2$ so $5|b_0$. The integers $d_1 = d_0/5, b_1 = b_0/5, c_1 = c_0/5$ satisfy

$$d_1^2 + 5b_1^2 + 8c_1^2 = 2 \cdot 5^{2(k-1)+1}(5l + r).$$

Repeating this process k times, we obtain integers d_k, b_k, c_k satisfying

$$d_k^2 + 5b_k^2 + 8c_k^2 = 2 \cdot 5(5l + r).$$

This equation is also valid for $k = 0$. Then $5|d_k^2 + 3c_k^2$ and so $5|d_k$ and $5|c_k$. Hence modulo 25 we deduce

$$5b_k^2 \equiv 10r \pmod{25}$$

so that

$$b_k^2 \equiv 2r \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{5},$$

which is impossible. Thus positive integers n in the progressions $5^{2k+1}(5l + 1)$ and $5^{2k+1}(5l + 4)$ are not represented by $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$. Hence the progressions corresponding to $2x^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2 + 2xy$ are precisely $4l + 1$ and $25^k(25l + 5r)$ ($r = 1, 4$). □

Proof of no. 53. We give a compact proof based on the result [6, p. 112] that $n = u^2 + 5v^2 + 10w^2$ for some integers u, v and w if and only if $n \neq 25^k(5l \pm 2)$ for any $k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} n = 2x^2 + 3y^2 + 5z^2 + 2xy &\iff 2n = (2x + y)^2 + 5y^2 + 10z^2 \\ &\iff 2n = u^2 + 5y^2 + 10z^2, u \equiv y \pmod{2} \\ &\iff 2n = u^2 + 5y^2 + 10z^2 \\ &\iff 2n \neq 25^k(5l_1 \pm 2) \\ &\iff 2n \neq 25^k(10l \pm 2) \\ &\iff n \neq 25^k(5l \pm 1). \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of no. 55. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Suppose that $n = x^2 + xy + y^2$ for some integers x and y . Then $n = u^2 + 3v^2$, where u and v are the integers given by

$$\begin{cases} u = \frac{x}{2} + y, v = \frac{x}{2} & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ u = x + \frac{y}{2}, v = \frac{y}{2} & \text{if } y \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ u = \frac{x-y}{2}, v = \frac{-x-y}{2} & \text{if } x \equiv y \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Now suppose that $n = u^2 + 3v^2$ for some integers u and v . Then $n = x^2 + xy + y^2$, where x and y are the integers given by $x = u - v, y = -u - v$. This proves that the forms $x^2 + xy + y^2$ and $x^2 + 3y^2$ represent exactly the same positive integers. Hence the ternary quadratic forms $x^2 + 6(y^2 + yz + z^2)$ and $x^2 + 6(y^2 + 3z^2)$ represent exactly the same positive integers. By [6, p. 112] the latter form $x^2 + 6y^2 + 18z^2$ represents precisely all positive integers $n \neq 3l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$. Hence $x^2 + 6y^2 + 6z^2 + 6yz$ represents all positive integers $n \neq 3l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$. □

Proof of no. 667. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $n \neq 9^k(9l + 6)$. Then $4n \neq 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$ for any $k, l \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Hence $4n = u^2 + 3v^2 + 4w^2$ for some integers u, v and w [6, p. 112]. Clearly $u \equiv v \pmod{2}$ so we can define integers x, y and z by $x = (u - v)/2, y = v, z = w$. Then $u = 2x + y, v = y, w = z$ so $4n = (2x + y)^2 + 3y^2 + 4z^2$ and thus $n = x^2 + xy + y^2 + z^2$ so n is represented by $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + xy$. The steps are easily reversed to show that $n = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + xy$ implies $n \neq 9^k(9l + 6)$. □

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Appendix

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
1	1	1	1	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 7)$	1
2	1	1	2	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 14)$	2
3	1	1	3	0	0	0	$9^k(9l + 6)$	3
4	1	2	2	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5)$	3
5	1	1	4	0	0	0	$8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	4
6	1	2	2	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 7)$	4
7	1	1	5	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 3)$	5
8	1	2	3	2	0	0	$25^k(25l \pm 5)$	5
9	1	1	6	0	0	0	$9^k(9l + 3)$	6
10	1	2	3	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 10)$	6
11	2	2	3	2	2	2	$4^k(8l + 1)$	7
12	1	1	8	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	8
13	1	2	4	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 14)$	8
14	1	3	3	2	0	0	$8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	8
15	2	2	3	2	2	0	$4l + 1, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	8
16	1	1	9	0	0	0	$9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	9
17	1	2	5	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 7)$	9
18	1	3	3	0	0	0	$9^k(3l + 2)$	9
19	2	2	3	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 7)$	9
20	1	2	5	0	0	0	$25^k(25l \pm 10)$	10
21	1	2	6	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5)$	11
22	1	1	12	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	12
23	1	2	6	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5)$	12
24	1	3	4	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	12
25	1	4	4	4	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	12
26	2	2	3	0	0	0	$8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	12
27	2	3	3	2	2	2	$8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5)$	12
28	1	3	5	2	0	0	$4^k(16l + 2)$	14
29	2	2	5	0	0	2	$4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	15
30	2	3	3	0	0	2	$4^k(8l + 1)$	15
31	1	1	16	0	0	0	$8l + 3, 8l + 6, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
32	1	2	8	0	0	0	$8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
33	1	4	4	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
34	1	4	5	4	0	0	$8l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
35	2	3	3	2	0	0	$8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
36	3	3	3	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	16
37	1	3	6	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 14)$	18
38	2	3	3	0	0	0	$9^k(3l + 1)$	18
39	1	2	10	0	0	0	$8l + 7, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20
40	1	3	7	2	0	0	$4l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
41	2	3	4	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20
42	3	3	3	2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20
43	1	1	21	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	21
44	2	3	5	2	0	2	$4^k(8l + 1)$	23
45	1	1	24	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	24
46	1	4	6	0	0	0	$16l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	24
47	1	4	7	4	0	0	$4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	24
48	1	5	5	2	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	24
49	2	2	7	2	2	0	$4l + 1, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	24
50	3	3	3	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	24
	1	2	13	2	0	0	$25l + 5r (r = 1, 2, 3, 4), 4^k(8l + 7)$	25
51								
52	1	5	5	0	0	0	$5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	25
53	2	3	5	0	0	2	$25^k(5l \pm 1)$	25
54	1	3	9	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
55	1	6	6	6	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	27
56	2	2	9	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	27
57	2	3	5	0	2	0	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
58	1	4	8	4	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	28
59	2	3	5	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 1)$	28
60	2	3	6	2	0	2	$8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 1)$	28
61	1	3	10	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	30
62	1	2	16	0	0	0	$8l + 5, 8l + 7, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
63	1	4	8	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
64	1	6	6	4	0	0	$8l \pm 3, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
65	2	3	7	2	2	2	$4l + 1, 16l + 4, 16l + 6, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
66	2	4	5	4	0	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
67	3	3	4	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
68	3	3	5	-2	2	2	$8l \pm 1, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
69	1	2	18	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5), 25^k(25l \pm 10), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	35
70	1	3	12	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	36
71	1	6	6	0	0	0	$8l + 3, 9^k(3l + 2)$	36
72	2	3	6	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 7)$	36
73	2	5	5	4	2	2	$3l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	36
74	3	3	4	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 9^k(3l + 2)$	36
75	3	4	4	4	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	36
76	2	3	7	0	2	0	$4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(169l + 13r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	39
77	1	5	8	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	40
78	3	3	6	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	40

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
79	1	6	9	6	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3)$	45
80	2	2	15	0	0	2	$4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	45
81	1	4	12	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
82	1	4	13	4	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
83	1	8	8	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	48
84	2	3	10	2	0	2	$8l + 1, 8l + 6, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	48
85	2	3	8	0	0	0	$8l \pm 1, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
86	2	5	5	2	0	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
87	3	3	6	2	2	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 2, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	48
88	3	3	7	-2	2	2	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5)$	48
89	3	4	4	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
90	4	4	5	4	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48
91	3	5	5	-4	2	2	$7l + r, (r = 1, 2, 4) 4^k(8l + 7)$	49
92	1	5	10	0	0	0	$25^k(5l \pm 2)$	50
93	3	3	7	2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 169^k(169l + 13r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	52
94	1	3	18	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 10)$	54
95	1	6	9	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	54
96	2	3	9	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 10)$	54
97	2	5	6	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 3)$	54
98	1	5	12	4	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2)$	56
99	3	4	6	4	2	0	$4l + 1, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2)$	56
100	1	4	16	4	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 3)$	60
101	2	5	6	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	60
102	2	6	7	6	2	0	$8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	60
103	2	5	7	2	2	0	$9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	63
104	3	3	7	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	63
105	1	2	32	0	0	0	$8l + 5, 16l + 10, 16l + 14, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
106	1	4	16	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
107	1	5	13	2	0	0	$8l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 8, 32l + 12, 128l + 48, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
108	1	8	8	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
109	2	3	11	2	0	0	$8l + 1, 16l \pm 6, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
110	3	3	8	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
111	3	5	5	2	2	2	$8l + 1, 16l \pm 2, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
112	4	5	5	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	64
113	1	9	9	6	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 3, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	72
114	2	3	12	0	0	0	$16l + 6, 9^k(3l + 1)$	72
115	3	3	8	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	72
116	3	4	7	4	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	72

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
117	3	5	5	2	0	0	$4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	72
118	5	5	5	-2	4	4	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	72
119	1	10	10	10	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	75
120	2	3	15	0	0	2	$5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 5)$	75
121	1	8	12	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	80
122	3	3	11	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	80
123	3	4	7	0	2	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	80
124	3	6	6	-4	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 4, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	80
125	4	4	7	4	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3)$	80
126	1	9	9	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	81
127	2	3	14	0	2	0	$3l + 1, 9l + 6, 27l + 9, 4^k(8l + 7)$	81
128	2	5	9	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	81
129	3	3	11	2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	84
130	1	3	30	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	90
131	1	10	10	4	0	0	$8l + 5, 8l + 7, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
132	1	4	24	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
133	1	6	16	0	0	0	$8l \pm 3, 16l \pm 2, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
134	2	7	8	4	0	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 6, 16l + 4, 32l + 24, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
135	4	4	7	0	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
136	4	5	6	0	0	4	$8l \pm 1, 16l \pm 2, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
137	4	5	7	2	4	4	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	96
138	3	5	7	0	0	2	$7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(16l + 14)$	98
139	2	3	20	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
140	2	5	10	0	0	0	$8l + 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
141	3	5	7	0	2	0	$4l + 2, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
142	3	7	7	-6	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
143	1	12	12	12	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
144	1	3	36	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
145	1	4	28	4	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
146	1	6	18	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	108
147	1	9	12	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
148	2	3	18	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
149	2	5	12	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
150	2	6	11	6	2	0	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	108
151	2	6	9	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	108
152	3	4	10	4	0	0	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
153	3	5	8	4	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
154	4	6	7	6	4	0	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	108
155	5	5	5	-2	2	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	108
156	3	6	7	2	2	2	$8l + 2, 8l + 5, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 1)$	112
157	3	7	7	6	2	2	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 1)$	112

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
158	5	5	5	2	2	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	112
159	1	6	21	6	0	0	$4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 2), 169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	117
160	1	12	13	12	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	120
161	3	4	11	4	0	0	$4l + 1, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	120
162	2	6	11	0	0	2	$11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $4^k(8l + 7)$	121
163	1	5	25	0	0	0	$5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	125
164	2	5	13	0	2	0	$5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	125
165	1	8	16	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 8l + 5, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
166	3	3	16	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
167	3	4	11	0	2	0	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 8, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
168	3	5	10	4	0	2	$8l \pm 1, 16l + 2, 32l \pm 4, 64l + 8, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
169	3	7	7	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 4, 16l + 6, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
170	4	5	8	0	0	4	$4l + 3, 8l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
171	4	7	7	6	4	4	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	128
172	4	7	7	6	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	132
173	2	3	23	0	2	0	$3l + 1, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1)$	135
174	3	7	7	4	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1)$	135
175	6	6	7	6	6	6	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	135
176	1	4	36	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
177	1	12	12	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
178	1	6	24	0	0	0	$8l \pm 3, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
179	2	5	17	4	2	2	$3l + 1, 8l + 3, 8l + 6, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
180	3	3	19	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
181	3	4	12	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
182	3	7	7	2	0	0	$4l + 1, 8l + 6, 16l + 4, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
183	3	8	8	8	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
184	4	4	11	4	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
185	4	6	7	0	4	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
186	4	7	7	2	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
187	5	5	8	-4	4	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
188	5	5	8	4	4	4	$3l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	144
189	3	7	7	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	147
190	2	5	15	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	150
191	3	6	11	6	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 4, 32l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	160

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
192	5	6	6	2	0	0	$4^k(8l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	175
193	1	8	24	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	176
194	2	6	15	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	180
195	2	6	17	6	2	0	$8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	180
196	3	8	8	4	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	180
197	4	7	8	4	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	180
198	1	9	21	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	189
199	2	5	21	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	189
200	1	8	24	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	192
201	1	16	16	16	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
202	2	5	20	4	0	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 10, 16l + 14, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
203	3	3	24	0	0	2	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 5)$	192
204	3	7	11	6	2	2	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	192
205	3	8	8	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
206	4	5	13	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
207	4	7	8	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	192
208	5	5	8	0	0	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
209	5	7	7	6	2	2	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
210	7	7	7	-2	6	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	192
211	3	5	14	0	0	2	$7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(8l + 7)$	196
212	4	7	8	0	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	196
213	5	5	10	-2	2	4	$7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	196
214	1	5	40	0	0	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 2, 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	200
215	4	6	11	2	4	4	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	200
216	1	12	21	12	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
217	1	9	24	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
218	2	11	11	4	2	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
219	2	5	24	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 3, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
220	3	4	19	4	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
221	3	8	11	8	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
222	4	7	10	2	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 8l + 6, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
223	5	5	9	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 3, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
224	5	6	8	0	4	0	$3l + 1, 16l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
225	5	8	8	8	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
226*	3	6	14	4	2	2	$4l + 1, 16l + 4, 16l + 10, 64l + 40, 4^k(16l + 2)$	224

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
227	3	10	10	10	0	0	$4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	225
228	5	6	9	6	0	0	$3l+1, 5l\pm 2, 4^k(8l+7)$	225
229	2	7	19	2	2	2	$8l+5, 8l+6, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	240
230	5	5	12	-4	4	2	$4l+2, 4l+3, 4^k(8l+1)$	240
231	5	8	8	8	0	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	240
232	6	7	8	4	0	6	$8l+2, 8l+5, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	240
233	7	7	8	-4	4	6	$4l+2, 8l+5, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	240
234	2	9	14	0	2	0	$3l+1, 9l\pm 3, 4^k(8l+5)$	243
235	6	6	7	0	0	2	$4^k(8l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 5), 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r=1, 2, 4$)	245
236	5	8	8	4	4	4	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 49^k(49l+7r)$ ($r=3, 5, 6$)	252
237	1	16	16	0	0	0	$4l+2, 8l\pm 3, 16l+8, 32l+12, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
238	1	8	32	0	0	0	$4l+2, 8l\pm 3, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
239	3	3	32	0	0	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
240	3	11	11	-10	2	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 16l+4, 16l+8, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
241	3	8	11	0	2	0	$4l+1, 4l+2, 32l+4, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
242	4	5	16	0	0	4	$4l+2, 8l+1, 8l+3, 16l+8, 32l+12, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
243	5	5	12	4	4	2	$4l+2, 8l+1, 8l+3, 32l+4, 4^k(8l+7)$	256
244	3	9	11	6	0	0	$3l+1, 4^k(16l+2), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	270
245	2	12	15	12	0	0	$8l\pm 3, 16l\pm 6, 64l+24, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
246	2	3	48	0	0	0	$8l\pm 1, 16l\pm 6, 64l+24, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
247	3	8	12	0	0	0	$4l+1, 4l+2, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
248	3	8	14	8	0	0	$8l+5, 8l+7, 16l+2, 16l+6, 64l+24, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
249	5	5	12	0	0	2	$4l+2, 4l+3, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
250	5	5	14	-4	4	2	$8l+1, 8l+3, 16l+2, 16l+6, 64l+24, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
251	5	5	14	2	2	4	$4l+3, 8l+2, 16l+12, 32l+8, 9^k(3l+1)$	288
252	1	10	30	0	0	0	$4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(5l\pm 2)$	300
253	4	10	11	10	4	0	$8l+1, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(5l\pm 2)$	300
254	5	8	8	4	0	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 5l\pm 1, 9^k(9l+6)$	300
255	1	8	40	0	0	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 32l+28, 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	320
256	3	11	11	6	2	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 16l+4, 16l+8, 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	320
257	4	8	13	8	4	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+1, 32l+28, 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	320

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
258	7	7	7	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	320
259	3	4	28	4	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 6, 9^k(3l + 2)$	324
260	4	7	15	6	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 3, 9^k(3l + 2)$	324
261	4	4	23	4	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	336
262	2	11	18	8	2	2	$7l + r (r = 3, 5, 6), 49l + 7r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(8l + 1)$	343
263	3	5	26	-4	2	2	$7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 49l + 7r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(8l + 1)$	343
264	3	7	18	6	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(169l + 13r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	351
265	1	12	33	12	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	360
266	3	4	31	4	0	0	$4l + 1, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	360
267	5	8	12	8	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	368
268	2	5	38	0	2	0	$5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	375
269	5	6	14	6	0	0	$5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	375
270	6	6	11	2	2	2	$5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(8l + 1)$	375
271	1	16	24	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
272	4	11	11	6	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
273	4	5	24	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
274	4	7	15	6	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
275	4	7	16	0	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
276	5	7	13	-6	2	2	$2^k(8l + 1) (k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 5), 2^k(8l + 3) (k = 0, 1, 2, 3), 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
277	7	8	8	0	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 4, 32l + 24, 9^k(9l + 3)$	384
278	3	7	19	0	2	0	$4l + 1, 7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	392
279	5	10	10	-8	2	2	$4l + 3, 7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	392
280	5	5	17	-2	2	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(3l + 1)$	396
281	3	3	51	-2	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 25l \pm 5, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 7)$	400
282	3	7	20	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	400
283	3	7	22	-6	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 4, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	400
284	4	11	11	2	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	400
285	5	8	12	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	400
286	7	7	12	-4	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	400
287	2	14	17	10	2	2	$9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	405
288	1	12	36	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
289	1	24	24	24	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
290	2	11	23	10	2	2	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 8l + 6, 9l + 3, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
291	3	10	16	8	0	0	$3l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
292	3	4	36	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
293	3	8	20	8	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
294	4	12	13	12	4	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
295	4	7	19	2	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
296	5	5	20	-4	4	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
297	5	8	12	0	0	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
298	5	8	14	8	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 3, 8l + 2, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
299	6	7	15	6	6	6	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 2, 9l + 3, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
300	6	8	11	4	6	0	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 8l + 2, 9l + 3, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
301	7	7	10	-2	2	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 8l + 6, 9l + 3, 16l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
302	7	7	10	4	4	2	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
303	8	8	11	4	8	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
304	8	8	9	0	0	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	432
305	1	21	21	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	441
306	5	10	10	6	2	2	$7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	441
307	5	8	12	0	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	448
308	3	8	19	0	2	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 1)$	448
309	4	5	29	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	448
310	7	7	12	4	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	448
311	5	6	15	0	0	0	$4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	450
312	3	7	27	-6	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	500
313	4	11	15	10	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	500
314	2	7	39	0	0	2	$4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	507
315	1	8	64	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 32l + 20, 32l + 28, 64l + 40, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
316	3	11	16	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
317	3	11	19	-10	2	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 6, 32l \pm 4, 64l + 8, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
318	4	7	23	6	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l \pm 12, 64l + 8, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
319	5	12	12	-8	4	4	$4l + 3, 8l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l \pm 4, 64l + 8, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
320	5	8	13	0	2	0	$4l + 3, 8l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 40, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
321	7	7	12	-4	4	2	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 6, 32l + 8, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
322	7	7	15	-2	6	6	$4l + 1, 8l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 6, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 40, 4^k(16l + 14)$	512
323	5	10	14	10	2	4	$23l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 13, 16, 18$), $4^k(8l + 7)$	529
324	5	8	17	8	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 3)$	540
325	6	7	13	2	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	540
326	6	7	18	6	0	6	$3l + 2, 8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	540
327	1	8	72	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 25^k(25l \pm 10), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	560
328	7	7	13	-2	2	4	$3l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	567
329	3	8	24	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7)$	576
330	1	24	24	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
331	3	16	16	16	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
332	4	13	13	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
333	4	7	24	0	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
334	5	5	24	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	576
335	5	8	17	-4	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	576
336	6	7	15	6	0	0	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 10, 16l + 14, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 48, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
337	7	10	10	-4	4	4	$8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 48, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
338	7	7	15	-6	6	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	576
339	8	9	9	6	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	576
340	5	12	12	-4	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	588
341	5	8	17	8	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	600
342	7	7	15	0	0	6	$4l + 1, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	600
343	5	5	28	-4	4	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	624
344	2	15	23	0	2	0	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	675
345	7	7	15	0	0	4	$3l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	675
346	9	11	11	-8	6	6	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	675
347	7	8	15	8	2	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	676

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
348	2	17	24	12	0	2	$8l + 6, 8l + 7, 32l + 28, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	720
349	4	7	31	2	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3)$	720
350	6	8	17	4	6	0	$8l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 28, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	720
351	8	8	15	0	0	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	720
352	8	8	17	4	8	8	$4l + 2, 8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	720
353	4	15	16	12	4	0	$3l+2, 4l+1, 4l+2, 9l+3, 49^k(49l+7r)$ $(r = 1, 2, 4)$	756
354	8	11	11	2	4	8	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 9l+3, 49^k(49l+7r)$ $(r = 1, 2, 4)$	756
355	1	16	48	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	768
356	3	11	27	-10	2	2	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	768
357	5	13	13	-6	2	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	768
358	5	8	20	0	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	768
359	7	12	12	-8	4	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	768
360	7	7	16	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 6)$	768
361	7	7	20	4	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	768
362	3	19	19	-18	2	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(8l+7)$	784
363	5	10	17	6	2	2	$7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l+3, 8l+6, 32l+12, 4^k(8l+7)$	784
364	5	12	17	12	2	4	$4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l+3, 4^k(8l+7)$	784
365	6	11	14	-6	4	2	$4l+1, 8l+2, 16l+4, 32l+8, 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	800
366	7	12	12	8	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 169^k(169l \pm 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	832
367	5	14	14	4	4	4	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
368	5	6	29	0	2	0	$3l + 1, 8l \pm 1, 16l \pm 2, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
369	5	8	24	0	0	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
370	6	9	17	6	0	0	$3l + 1, 8l \pm 3, 16l \pm 2, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
371	7	10	15	-6	6	2	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 8l + 6, 16l + 4, 32l + 24, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
372	8	11	11	-2	4	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
373	9	11	11	-2	6	6	$3l + 1, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 64l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	864
374	10	12	13	12	10	0	$8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	900
375	3	10	30	0	0	0	$4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	900
376	4	15	16	0	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	900
377	7	7	23	-2	2	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	900
378	5	8	24	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	960
379	4	5	61	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 3)$	960
380	7	7	24	0	0	6	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	960
381	7	8	19	4	2	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	960
382	8	11	11	2	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	960
383	5	8	29	8	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	972
384	7	8	20	0	4	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	1008
385	12	12	13	12	12	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	1008
386	5	8	28	8	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	1008
387	3	11	32	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1024
388	5	12	20	8	4	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 64l \pm 8, 128l + 16, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1024
389	5	13	20	-12	4	2	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1024
390	5	10	21	0	0	2	$7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1029
391	3	11	35	10	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1080
392	9	12	14	12	6	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 3, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1080
393	2	15	38	0	2	0	$5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1125
394	6	14	15	0	0	6	$5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1125
395	7	13	13	-4	2	2	$3l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	1125
396	3	8	48	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 64l + 24, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
397	5	12	20	0	4	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
398	5	14	20	-8	4	4	$2^k(8l + 1) (k = 0, 1, 2, 3), 2^k(8l + 3) (k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 5), 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
399	5	17	17	-14	2	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 16l + 12, 32l + 8, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
400	5	5	48	0	0	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 64l + 24, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
401	8	12	15	12	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 64l + 24, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
402	8	12	17	12	8	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 64l + 24, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1152
403	8	11	15	6	0	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1188

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
404	1	40	40	40	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1200
405	10	11	16	8	0	10	$8l + 1, 8l + 6, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1200
406	11	11	14	-6	6	8	$8l + 1, 8l + 2, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1200
407	4	11	31	2	4	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1200
408	8	12	17	4	8	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1200
409	7	13	18	-12	6	2	$3l + 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	1215
410	2	18	35	0	0	2	$4^k(8l + 7), 25^k(5l \pm 1), 49^k(7l + r), (r = 3, 5, 6)$	1225
411	7	12	16	0	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1280
412	4	13	29	10	4	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1280
413	7	15	15	-2	6	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(8l + 3)$	1280
414	5	8	36	0	0	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1296
415	3	8	56	8	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 6, 27l + 9, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1296
416	4	19	19	2	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1296
417	8	11	20	4	8	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	1296
418	3	14	35	14	0	0	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r), (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1323
419	3	7	63	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r), (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1323
420	12	12	15	12	12	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 49^k(49l + 7r), (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1344
421	7	13	15	0	0	2	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1350
422	8	13	17	2	4	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 11l + r, (r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9), 9^k(9l + 6)$	1452
423	8	13	17	2	8	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 5, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1500
424	6	13	21	0	6	0	$4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 169^k(13l + r), (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	1521
425	11	11	16	-8	8	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l \pm 4, 64l \pm 8, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
426	11	11	16	8	8	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
427	4	11	40	8	0	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 20, 32l + 28, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
428	5	13	24	0	0	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l \pm 4, 64l \pm 8, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
429	5	13	28	-12	4	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
430	7	15	16	0	0	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
431	7	15	20	-12	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1536
432	3	27	27	-26	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1600
433	5	8	40	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 12, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1600
434	7	12	23	12	2	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1600
435	8	17	17	14	8	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 32l + 12, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1600
436	8	11	23	2	4	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1620
437	1	24	72	0	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
438	1	48	48	48	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
439	5	5	72	0	0	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
440	8	9	24	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
441	1	16	112	16	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 9l + 3, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
442	4	13	37	2	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
443	12	13	16	8	0	12	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
444	3	16	40	16	0	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
445	3	8	72	0	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
446	4	19	24	0	0	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
447	4	7	72	0	0	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
448	5	20	20	-8	4	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
449	7	10	28	8	4	4	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
450	7	13	21	6	6	2	$3l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 10, 16l + 14, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
451	7	15	19	-6	2	6	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 9l + 3, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
452	7	7	39	-6	6	2	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
453	8	11	23	10	4	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 9l + 3, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
454	8	11	24	0	0	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
455	8	12	23	12	8	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
456	8	15	15	6	0	0	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	1728
457	9	17	17	-14	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	1728
458	8	11	23	2	8	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	1764
459	7	12	23	-4	2	4	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 1)$	1792
460	11	11	15	0	0	2	$4l + 1, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1800
461	5	21	21	18	0	0	$4l + 3, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1800
462	4	7	79	2	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 2), 169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	1872
463	8	11	24	0	8	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $4^k(8l + 7)$	1936
464	4	20	31	20	4	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	2000
465	7	7	52	-4	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	2000
466	10	13	22	8	10	10	$9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	2025
467	7	12	28	-8	4	4	$2^i(4l + 1)$ ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$), $2^i(8l + 3)$ ($i = 0, 1, 3, 5$), $4^k(16l + 14)$	2048
468	7	15	23	10	2	6	$2^i(8l + r)$ ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3; r = 1, 3, 5$), $4^k(16l + 14)$	2048
469	7	15	23	-6	2	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	2112
470	11	11	19	2	2	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	2112
471	12	13	21	6	12	12	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1)$	2160
472	13	13	13	2	2	2	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	2160
473	5	5	92	-4	4	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1)$	2160
474	7	18	19	6	2	6	$3l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 6, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	2160
475	7	19	19	14	2	2	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 5, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	2160
476	3	16	48	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	2304
477	11	16	16	0	8	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(8l + 7)$	2304
478	13	13	16	8	8	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 48, 9^k(3l + 2)$	2304

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
479	4	13	48	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	2304
480	5	20	29	20	2	4	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	2304
481	7	15	24	0	0	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 48, 9^k(3l + 2)$	2304
482	7	15	28	-12	4	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 9^k(3l + 2)$	2304
483	9	17	17	2	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	2304
484	12	17	17	6	12	12	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	2352
485	11	11	26	-2	2	8	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	2700
486	12	13	25	10	0	12	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	2700
487	9	11	30	0	0	6	$3l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	2700
488	5	24	24	8	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	2800
489	11	16	19	8	2	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
490	8	15	24	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
491	12	15	23	6	12	12	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 1)$	2880
492	7	16	31	16	6	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
493	8	17	24	0	0	8	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
494	8	17	24	12	0	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 28, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
495	8	21	21	18	0	0	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2880
496	4	31	31	26	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	3024
497	8	20	23	4	8	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	3024
498	7	20	23	-4	2	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 128l + 16, 128l + 48, 512l + 64, 9^k(9l + 6)$	3072
499	7	23	23	-18	2	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	3072
500	7	15	30	6	0	0	$7l + r (r = 3, 5, 6), 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	3087

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
501	3	19	56	0	0	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(8l+7)$	3136
502	11	11	32	-8	8	6	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 16l+4, 16l+8, 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	3136
503	12	17	20	4	8	12	$4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l\pm 3, 4^k(8l+7)$	3136
504	5	12	56	0	0	4	$4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l+1, 8l+3, 4^k(8l+7)$	3136
505	10	19	21	6	0	10	$3l+2, 5l\pm 2, 9l+6, 25l\pm 5, 4^k(8l+1)$	3375
506	11	14	26	14	2	4	$3l+1, 5l\pm 2, 9l+6, 25l\pm 5, 4^k(8l+1)$	3375
507	6	19	34	8	6	6	$3l+2, 5l\pm 2, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	3375
508	7	13	42	-12	6	2	$3l+2, 5l\pm 1, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	3375
509	11	11	32	-8	8	2	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 64l+8, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
510	11	15	23	-6	2	6	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 16l+8, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
511	15	15	20	12	12	6	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+3, 64l+8, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
512	5	24	29	0	2	0	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+1, 64l+8, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
513	8	11	44	8	8	4	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 16l+4, 32l+24, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
514	9	17	24	0	0	6	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 64l+8, 9^k(9l+3)$	3456
515	10	13	37	8	10	10	$8l+3, 8l+6, 32l+12, 4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	3600
516	11	11	35	-10	10	2	$3l+1, 4l+1, 4l+2, 5l\pm 2, 4^k(8l+7)$	3600
517	12	13	33	6	12	12	$4l+2, 8l+3, 4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	3600
518	13	13	22	-2	2	4	$8l+2, 8l+3, 32l+12, 4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	3600
519	3	40	40	40	0	0	$4l+1, 4l+2, 4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	3600
520	11	19	19	6	2	2	$4l+2, 8l+5, 8l+7, 16l+8, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	3840
521	7	23	31	-22	6	2	$4l+2, 8l\pm 3, 16l+8, 32l+20, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	3840
522	8	9	56	0	8	0	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 9l\pm 3, 4^k(8l+5)$	3888
523	7	24	24	8	0	0	$4l+1, 4l+2, 4^k(8l+3), 25^k(25l\pm 5), 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	3920
524	10	13	34	2	10	4	$3l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $9l\pm 3, 4^k(8l+7)$	3969

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dxy + eyz + fzx$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
525	5	29	29	10	2	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	4032
526	7	19	39	-18	6	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $9^k(3l + 2)$	4356
527	11	11	39	6	6	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 10, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4500
528	7	18	39	0	0	6	$3l + 2, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	4563
529	12	17	32	16	0	12	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 32l + 20, 32l + 28, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
530	15	20	20	8	12	12	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
531	17	17	20	-4	4	14	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
532	5	20	48	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
533	5	20	53	20	2	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
534	8	15	39	6	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l \pm 12, 64l \pm 24, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
535	8	17	41	10	8	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 32l \pm 12, 64l \pm 24, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4608
536	1	40	120	0	0	0	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	4800
537	11	16	31	8	2	8	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	4800
538	17	17	25	-10	10	14	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	4800
539	4	11	120	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	4800
540	4	31	40	0	0	4	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	4800
541	13	16	29	8	10	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 4, 128l + 112, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	5120
542	3	16	112	16	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 9l + 6, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	5184
543	7	15	55	6	-2	6	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	5184
544	16	19	27	18	0	16	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 9l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	5184
545	13	13	33	-6	6	2	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	5292
546	5	17	68	-16	4	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	5292

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
547	16	16	23	8	8	0	$4l+1, 4l+2, 16l+4, 16l+8, 4^k(8l+3), 9^k(9l+6), 49^k(49l+7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	5376
548	13	22	22	-16	2	2	$3l+2, 4l+3, 16l+2, 4^k(16l+10), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	5400
549	7	15	52	0	4	0	$3l+2, 4l+1, 16l+2, 4^k(16l+10), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	5400
550	5	12	101	12	2	4	$4l+2, 4l+3, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $49l+7r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(8l+1)$	5488
551	8	21	37	14	8	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 7l+r$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$), $49l+7r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(8l+1)$	5488
552	12	21	28	12	0	12	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+6), 169^k(169l+13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	5616
553	21	21	21	2	18	18	$4l+2, 4l+3, 5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(8l+1)$	6000
554	5	24	56	24	0	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	6000
555	5	8	152	8	0	0	$4l+2, 4l+3, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l+1), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	6000
556	9	11	71	-8	6	6	$3l+1, 9l+3, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	6075
557	11	16	43	-8	10	8	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 16l+4, 16l+8, 32l+28, 256l+32, 9^k(9l+3)$	6144
558	11	19	32	-8	8	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 16l+4, 16l+8, 64l+16, 128l+96, 9^k(9l+3)$	6144
559	5	20	68	-8	4	4	$4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+1, 16l+8, 16l+12, 9^k(3l+1)$	6336
560	17	20	20	-8	4	4	$4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 16l+8, 16l+12, 9^k(3l+1)$	6336
561	3	27	80	0	0	2	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 16l+4, 16l+8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	6400
562	11	16	44	16	4	8	$4l+1, 4l+2, 5l \pm 2, 16l+4, 16l+8, 4^k(8l+7)$	6400
563	17	17	32	16	16	14	$4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 16l+8, 16l+12, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	6400
564	8	23	39	6	0	8	$4l+1, 4l+2, 9l+6, 4^k(8l+3), 9^k(3l+1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	6480
565	1	48	144	0	0	0	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 16l+8, 16l+12, 9^k(9l+6)$	6912
566	9	17	48	0	0	6	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 16l+8, 16l+12, 9^k(9l+6)$	6912
567	5	20	77	20	2	4	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+1, 16l+8, 16l+12, 32l+4, 9^k(9l+6)$	6912
568	11	27	32	-24	8	6	$3l+1, 4l+2, 8l \pm 1, 9l+3, 16l+8, 32l+4, 4^k(8l+5)$	6912

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
569	12	23	32	16	0	12	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 6)$	6912
570	13	16	37	8	2	8	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 4, 9^k(9l + 6)$	6912
571	13	21	28	12	4	6	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	6912
572	15	23	23	14	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	6912
573	16	19	28	4	16	8	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	6912
574	7	15	76	-12	4	6	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5)$	6912
575	7	28	39	-12	6	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	6912
576	19	19	27	-6	6	18	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7)$	7056
577	4	43	43	2	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	7056
578	11	16	51	8	2	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	8000
579	15	16	39	16	10	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	8000
580	7	12	103	12	2	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	8000
581	7	27	52	-24	4	6	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	8100
582	8	28	41	4	8	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 169^k(13l + r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	8112
583	11	19	51	-14	6	10	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 23l + r (r = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 13, 16, 18), 4^k(8l + 7)$	8464
584	13	24	28	0	4	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	8640
585	19	19	28	4	4	14	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	8640
586	5	29	68	-28	4	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 3)$	8640
587	7	24	52	0	4	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	8640
588	13	28	28	-16	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 1)$	9072
589	13	16	52	16	4	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 4, 128l + 48, 9^k(3l + 2)$	9216
590	13	21	37	6	10	6	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 1, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 128l + 16, 128l + 48, 512l + 192, 9^k(3l + 2)$	9216

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
591	17	20	33	20	2	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	9408
592	11	26	39	6	6	2	$3l + 1, 8l + 1, 8l + 6, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	10800
593	11	35	39	-30	6	10	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	10800
594	25	25	28	-20	20	10	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	10800
595	8	17	92	4	8	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5)$	10800
596	9	41	41	-38	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	10800
597	11	19	59	-18	10	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	10816
598	17	32	32	32	8	16	$4l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 16l + 8, 32l + 28, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	11520
599	21	29	29	26	18	18	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 16l + 8, 32l + 28, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	11520
600	15	16	55	16	6	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	12096
601	15	23	44	-20	12	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	12096
602	17	20	41	-12	10	4	$4l + 2, 7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l \pm 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7)$	12544
603	13	21	52	12	8	6	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $9^k(9l + 6)$	13068
604	11	32	44	-16	4	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	13824
605	11	35	44	28	4	10	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 32l + 20, 32l + 28, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	13824
606	15	20	56	16	0	12	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 4, 32l + 12, 64l + 8, 64l + 24, 256l + 32, 9^k(9l + 3)$	13824
607	15	23	44	-4	12	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	13824
608	3	40	120	0	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400
609	7	23	92	12	4	2	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400
610	12	13	120	0	0	12	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400
611	12	33	40	0	0	12	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
612	13	33	37	-18	2	6	$4l + 2, 8l + 3, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400
613	16	19	64	8	16	16	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	14400
614	27	28	28	-24	12	12	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	14400
615	9	17	113	-14	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 9l + 3, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	15552
616	13	37	37	-22	2	2	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	16128
617	20	31	31	-22	4	4	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	16464
618	15	24	56	24	0	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	18000
619	7	52	52	-16	4	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	18000
620	8	15	152	0	8	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	18000
621	17	20	57	12	6	4	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 64l + 48, 128l + 32, 9^k(3l + 1)$	18432
622	17	32	41	16	10	16	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 20, 256l + 96, 9^k(3l + 1)$	18432
623	11	32	59	8	10	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	19008
624	11	16	124	16	4	8	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	19200
625	16	31	44	4	16	8	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 4, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	19200
626	13	28	61	28	2	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 9l + 6, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	19440
627	8	35	72	0	8	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7), 25^k(5l \pm 1), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	19600
628	16	19	76	4	16	8	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(8l + 7)$	20736
629	12	17	129	6	12	12	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	21168
630	12	28	73	28	12	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	21168
631	17	32	52	32	4	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 11l + r (r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9), 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	23232
632	13	32	68	32	4	8	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 8l + 1, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 25l \pm 5, 9^k(9l + 3)$	24000

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
633	19	19	84	-12	12	14	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 169^k(13l + r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	24336
634	17	32	57	-16	6	16	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 32l + 20, 128l + 48, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	25600
635	23	32	44	32	4	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	25920
636	23	32	47	16	22	16	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 3, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 128l + 16, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27648
637	11	32	92	32	4	8	$3l + 1, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 7, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	28224
638	16	31	71	22	8	8	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(8l + 3)$	32000
639	27	40	43	40	18	0	$4l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	32400
640	19	28	67	-4	10	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 8l + 5, 8l + 7, 16l + 8, 32l + 20, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	34560
641	17	41	68	-36	12	10	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	37632
642	9	41	120	0	0	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	43200
643	11	35	120	0	0	10	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	43200
644	25	48	52	48	20	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 8l + 5, 16l + 8, 16l + 12, 9^k(9l + 6)$	43200
645	36	39	44	12	24	36	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 4^k(8l + 5), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	43200
646	16	31	103	-10	8	8	$3l + 2, 4l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 4, 16l + 8, 4^k(8l + 3), 9^k(9l + 6), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	48384
647	28	37	60	12	0	28	$4l + 2, 4l + 3, 7l + r (r = 3, 5, 6), 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(3l + 2), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	49392
648	13	28	157	28	2	4	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	54000
649	21	29	101	-26	18	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 2, 9l + 6, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(8l + 1)$	54000
650	21	40	76	40	12	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 2, 9l + 6, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(8l + 1)$	54000
651	24	45	61	30	24	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 4l + 3, 5l \pm 2, 4^k(8l + 1), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	54000
652	13	37	132	-36	12	2	$4l + 2, 8l + 1, 8l + 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	57600
653	33	48	52	48	12	24	$4l + 2, 8l \pm 3, 16l + 8, 32l + 12, 4^k(8l + 7), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	57600

Table 1: Positive integers not represented by even regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
654	19	27	136	-24	16	6	$3l+2, 4l+1, 4l+2, 7l+r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $9l \pm 3, 4^k(8l+7)$	63504
655	19	28	139	28	2	4	$4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 11l+r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $16l+4, 16l+8, 9^k(3l+2)$	69696
656	39	44	44	8	12	12	$4l+1, 4l+2, 5l \pm 2, 8l+3, 16l+4, 16l+8, 25l \pm 10, 9^k(3l+1)$	72000
657	28	57	57	-42	12	12	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 169^k(13l+r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	73008
658	17	20	257	20	2	4	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 9l+3, 16l+8, 16l+12, 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	84672
659	33	52	52	-8	12	12	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 9l+3, 16l+8, 16l+12, 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	84672
660	9	41	281	-38	6	6	$3l+1, 4l+2, 4l+3, 9l+3, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	97200
661	16	43	172	4	16	8	$4l+1, 4l+2, 16l+4, 16l+8, 4^k(8l+7), 9^k(3l+2), 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	112896
662	27	28	187	28	6	12	$3l+2, 4l+1, 4l+2, 8l+7, 9l \pm 3, 16l+4, 16l+8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	129600
663	39	44	111	-36	6	12	$3l+1, 4l+2, 8l+1, 8l+3, 16l+8, 32l+4, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	172800
664	52	57	84	-12	24	36	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 8l+5, 11l+r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $16l+8, 16l+12, 9^k(9l+6)$	209088
665	48	73	112	56	0	24	$3l+2, 4l+2, 4l+3, 16l+8, 16l+12, 4^k(8l+5), 9^k(9l+6), 49^k(7l+r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	338688

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
666	1	1	1	1	1	1	$4^k(16l+14)$	2
667	1	1	1	0	0	1	$9^k(9l+6)$	3
668	1	1	2	1	1	1	$25^k(25l \pm 5)$	5
669	1	1	2	0	0	1	$4^k(16l+10)$	6
670	1	1	2	1	1	0	$9^k(9l+3)$	6
671	1	1	2	0	1	0	$49^k(49l+7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	7
672	1	1	3	1	1	1	$8l+2, 16l+6, 4^k(16l+14)$	8
673	1	1	3	0	0	1	$9^k(3l+2)$	9
674	1	1	3	1	1	0	$4^k(16l+6)$	10
675	1	2	2	2	1	1	$25^k(25l \pm 10)$	10
676	1	1	3	0	1	0	$121^k(121l+11r)$ ($r = 2, 6, 7, 8, 10$)	11
677	1	1	4	0	0	1	$4l+2, 9^k(9l+6)$	12

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
678	1	2	2	1	1	1	$9^k(9l + 6)$	12
679	1	2	2	1	0	1	$169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	13
680	1	1	5	1	1	1	$4^k(16l + 2)$	14
681	1	2	2	1	0	0	$25^k(25l \pm 10)$	15
682	1	1	4	0	1	0	$9^k(9l + 3)$	15
683	1	2	3	2	1	1	$289^k(289l + 17r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4, 8, 9, 13, 15, 16$)	17
684	1	1	5	1	1	0	$9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 14)$	18
685	1	1	6	0	0	1	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 14)$	18
686	1	2	3	2	1	0	$4^k(16l + 14)$	18
687	2	2	2	1	2	2	$9^k(3l + 1)$	18
688	1	1	7	1	1	1	$4l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20
689	1	2	3	1	0	1	$25^k(25l \pm 5)$	20
690	1	2	3	0	0	1	$9^k(9l + 6)$	21
691	1	2	3	1	1	0	$49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	21
692	1	2	3	0	1	0	$4^k(16l + 10)$	22
693	1	3	3	3	1	1	$8l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	24
694	1	2	4	2	1	1	$9^k(9l + 3)$	24
695	2	2	2	-1	1	1	$25^k(5l \pm 1)$	25
696	1	1	7	0	1	0	$9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
697	1	1	9	0	0	1	$3l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
698	1	2	4	1	0	1	$9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
699	1	3	3	3	0	0	$3l + 2, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
700	2	2	2	1	1	1	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	27
701	1	3	3	2	1	1	$4l + 2, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	28
702	1	1	10	0	0	1	$4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	30
703	1	3	3	1	1	1	$4^k(16l + 2)$	30
704	1	3	3	1	0	1	$8l + 2, 16l + 6, 32l + 8, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	32
705	1	2	5	1	1	1	$9^k(9l + 3)$	33
706	1	1	12	0	0	1	$4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	36
707	1	3	4	3	1	0	$9^k(3l + 2)$	36
708	1	3	4	2	0	1	$8l + 2, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6)$	40
709	1	1	11	1	1	0	$4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	42
710	1	3	4	0	0	1	$4l + 2, 121^k(121l + 11r)$ ($r = 2, 6, 7, 8, 10$)	44
711	1	3	4	0	1	0	$3l + 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	45
712	1	2	7	2	1	1	$9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	45
713	2	2	3	0	0	1	$9^k(3l + 1)$	45
714	1	3	5	3	1	1	$4^k(16l + 2)$	46
715	1	3	5	3	1	0	$4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 6)$	48

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
716	1	2	7	0	0	1	$49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	49
717	1	2	7	2	1	0	$25l + 5r$ ($r = 1, 2, 3, 4$), $4^k(16l + 14)$	50
718	1	4	4	3	1	1	$25^k(5l \pm 2)$	50
719	2	3	3	1	2	2	$5l \pm 1$, $4^k(16l + 14)$	50
720	1	3	5	1	1	1	$4l + 2$, $169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	52
721	1	1	18	0	0	1	$3l + 2$, $9l + 6$, $4^k(16l + 10)$	54
722	1	4	4	2	1	1	$3l + 2$, $9^k(9l + 3)$	54
723	2	2	5	1	2	2	$3l + 1$, $9^k(9l + 3)$	54
724	2	3	3	3	0	0	$3l + 1$, $9l + 6$, $4^k(16l + 10)$	54
725	1	3	5	1	1	0	$8l + 6$, $16l + 10$, $4^k(16l + 2)$	56
726	1	4	5	4	1	0	$4l + 2$, $9^k(9l + 3)$	60
727	1	3	6	3	0	0	$9^k(3l + 2)$	63
728	2	2	5	2	2	1	$3l + 1$, $49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	63
729	1	2	9	0	1	0	$4^k(16l + 10)$, $25^k(25l \pm 5)$, $49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	70
730	1	3	7	2	1	1	$8l + 2$, $16l + 6$, $4^k(16l + 14)$	72
731	1	3	7	3	1	0	$3l + 2$, $8l + 2$, $16l + 6$, $4^k(16l + 14)$	72
732	1	4	5	2	1	0	$8l + 2$, $9l \pm 3$, $16l + 6$, $4^k(16l + 14)$	72
733	2	2	5	1	1	1	$9^k(3l + 1)$	72
734	1	4	5	0	0	1	$25^k(5l \pm 2)$	75
735	2	2	5	0	0	1	$5l \pm 1$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	75
736	1	5	5	4	1	1	$4^k(16l + 2)$, $9^k(9l + 3)$, $169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11$)	78
737	1	3	7	1	1	0	$4l + 2$, $16l + 8$, $25^k(25l \pm 5)$	80
738	1	3	7	0	1	0	$9l + 6$, $9^k(3l + 2)$	81
739	1	4	6	3	0	1	$9l + 3$, $9^k(3l + 2)$	81
740	1	3	8	2	0	1	$4l + 2$, $49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	84
741	1	1	30	0	0	1	$4^k(16l + 6)$, $9^k(3l + 2)$, $25^k(25l \pm 10)$	90
742	2	3	5	3	2	0	$3l + 1$, $4^k(16l + 6)$	90
743	3	3	3	-1	1	1	$7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $4^k(16l + 14)$	98
744	2	3	5	3	1	0	$9^k(3l + 1)$	99
745	2	2	7	-1	1	1	$25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
746	3	3	3	1	1	1	$4l + 2$, $25^k(5l \pm 1)$	100
747	1	1	36	0	0	1	$3l + 2$, $4l + 2$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
748	1	3	10	3	1	0	$3l + 2$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
749	1	4	7	0	1	0	$4l + 2$, $9l + 3$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
750	1	5	7	5	1	1	$4l + 2$, $9l + 3$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
751	2	2	8	2	2	1	$3l + 1$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
752	3	3	5	3	3	3	$3l + 1$, $4l + 2$, $9^k(9l + 6)$	108
753	1	3	11	3	1	0	$8l + 6$, $16l + 10$, $4^k(16l + 2)$, $9^k(9l + 6)$, $25^k(25l \pm 5)$	120
754	1	3	11	0	0	1	$121^k(11l + r)$ ($r = 2, 6, 7, 8, 10$)	121

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
755	1	4	9	3	1	1	$5l \pm 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	125
756	2	3	7	3	1	2	$5l \pm 1, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	125
757	1	5	7	2	1	1	$9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 2)$	126
758	3	3	5	3	3	0	$4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(3l + 1), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	126
759	1	5	7	1	0	1	$4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	132
760	1	3	12	3	0	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 6, 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	135
761	2	2	9	0	0	1	$3l + 1, 9l + 6, 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	135
762	2	5	5	5	1	2	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 3)$	135
763	1	3	13	3	1	0	$4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(3l + 2)$	144
764	1	2	21	0	0	1	$7l + r$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$), $9^k(9l + 6)$	147
765	3	3	5	-2	2	1	$49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	147
766	1	5	9	5	1	0	$5l \pm 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	150
767	2	5	5	5	0	0	$4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	150
768	1	6	7	0	1	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 27l + 18, 4^k(16l + 14)$	162
769	1	7	7	5	1	1	$3l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 14)$	162
770	2	5	5	1	2	2	$3l + 1, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 14)$	162
771	1	4	11	2	1	0	$8l + 2, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3),$ $49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	168
772	2	5	5	-3	1	1	$169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12$)	169
773	1	7	7	3	0	1	$4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	180
774	3	5	5	5	3	3	$4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	180
775	2	3	8	0	1	0	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	189
776	1	4	13	2	1	1	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	189
777	2	5	5	1	1	1	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	189
778	1	7	9	7	1	0	$4l + 2, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	196
779	3	3	7	3	3	1	$5l \pm 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	200
780	1	3	19	3	1	0	$3l + 2, 8l + 6, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
781	3	5	5	2	3	3	$3l + 1, 8l + 6, 9l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10)$	216
782	2	5	6	3	0	1	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 3)$	216
783	2	2	15	0	0	1	$3l + 1, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	225
784	1	4	15	0	0	1	$5l \pm 2, 9^k(3l + 2)$	225
785	2	5	7	5	1	0	$9l \pm 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	225
786	2	3	11	3	2	0	$4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 1), 169^k(169l + 13r)$ ($r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11$)	234
787*	1	5	13	2	1	1	$4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	240
788	1	3	22	0	0	1	$11l + r$ ($r = 2, 6, 7, 8, 10$), $4^k(16l + 14)$	242
789	1	7	9	0	0	1	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	243
790	2	3	11	3	1	0	$3l + 1, 27l + 9, 9^k(9l + 6)$	243
791	2	5	8	5	1	2	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 9^k(9l + 6)$	243
792	1	9	9	8	1	1	$5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(16l + 6)$	250
793	2	3	13	1	2	2	$5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(16l + 6)$	250
794	3	5	5	1	0	3	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	252

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
795	1	6	13	6	1	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 4^k(16l + 2)$	270
796	3	3	11	3	3	3	$3l + 1, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	270
797	5	5	5	4	5	5	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(16l + 2)$	270
798	3	5	6	1	2	3	$289^k(17l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4, 8, 9, 13, 15, 16)$	289
799	5	5	5	-3	3	4	$4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	294
800*	1	6	13	3	1	0	$3l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	297
801	2	5	8	-2	1	1	$3l + 1, 9^k(9l + 3)$	297
802	3	5	7	5	3	0	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	300
803	1	7	13	5	1	1	$4l + 2, 9l + 3, 9^k(3l + 2)$	324
804	3	3	10	0	0	1	$4^k(16l + 2), 25^k(5l \pm 1), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	350
805	1	3	31	3	1	0	$8l + 2, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	360
806	2	7	7	3	1	1	$11l + r (r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9), 9^k(9l + 6)$	363
807	2	7	7	-1	1	1	$5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 5, 9^k(9l + 3)$	375
808	1	9	13	9	1	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	378
809	2	5	11	1	2	2	$3l + 1, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	378
810	3	3	12	-2	2	1	$7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14)$	392
811	3	5	8	2	0	3	$4l + 2, 9^k(3l + 1)$	396
812	3	3	12	2	2	1	$4l + 2, 16l + 8, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	400
813*	2	5	11	2	2	1	$9l + 3, 9^k(3l + 1)$	405
814	2	8	8	7	1	1	$3l + 1, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	405
815	1	3	37	3	1	0	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
816	3	5	9	3	0	3	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 6)$	432
817	3	6	7	0	0	3	$7l + r (r = 1, 2, 4), 9^k(3l + 2)$	441
818	2	8	8	-5	1	1	$3l + 1, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	441
819	3	7	7	4	3	3	$3l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(16l + 14)$	450
820	5	5	6	0	0	5	$4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	450
821	1	3	44	0	0	1	$4l + 2, 121^k(11l + r) (r = 2, 6, 7, 8, 10)$	484
822	1	7	18	0	0	1	$3l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 10)$	486
823	3	3	14	0	0	1	$4^k(16l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 10), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	490
824	1	9	15	5	0	1	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	500
825	3	7	7	1	2	3	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	500
826	3	5	11	4	3	3	$8l + 6, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(3l + 1), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	504
827	5	5	8	2	4	5	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	540
828	3	3	17	-1	1	1	$4l + 2, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	588

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
829	5	7	7	6	5	5	$8l+6, 16l+2, 4^k(16l+10), 9^k(9l+3), 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	600
830	1	7	25	5	1	1	$3l+2, 8l+2, 9l\pm 3, 16l+6, 4^k(16l+14)$	648
831	5	5	8	4	4	1	$3l+1, 8l+2, 9l\pm 3, 16l+6, 4^k(16l+14)$	648
832	1	4	45	0	0	1	$3l+2, 9l+3, 25^k(5l\pm 2)$	675
833	5	6	6	3	0	0	$3l+1, 9l+3, 25^k(5l\pm 2)$	675
834	3	7	10	5	0	3	$3l+2, 5l\pm 1, 9^k(9l+6)$	675
835	5	5	8	-2	2	3	$4l+2, 169^k(13l+r) (r = 1, 3, 4, 9, 10, 12)$	676
836	1	9	21	7	0	1	$7l+r (r = 3, 5, 6), 49l+7r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(16l+2)$	686
837	3	5	13	1	3	2	$7l+r (r = 1, 2, 4), 49l+7r (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(16l+2)$	686
838	5	5	9	3	3	4	$3l+1, 4^k(16l+2), 9^k(9l+3), 169^k(169l+13r) (r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11)$	702
839*	3	5	15	3	3	3	$4l+2, 16l+8, 9^k(3l+1)$	720
840	1	10	19	0	1	0	$5l\pm 2, 4^k(16l+2), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	750
841	3	3	22	2	2	1	$5l\pm 1, 25l\pm 10, 4^k(16l+2)$	750
842	3	7	10	0	0	3	$5l\pm 1, 4^k(16l+2), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	750
843	1	13	15	3	0	1	$3l+2, 4l+2, 9l+3, 49^k(49l+7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	756
844	5	5	8	2	2	1	$3l+1, 4l+2, 9l+3, 49^k(49l+7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	756
845	1	7	31	5	1	1	$9l+3, 4^k(16l+6), 9^k(3l+2), 25^k(25l\pm 10)$	810
846	2	11	11	1	2	2	$4^k(16l+14), 9^k(3l+1), 49^k(7l+r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	882
847	5	5	10	2	2	3	$7l+r (r = 1, 2, 4), 9l\pm 3, 4^k(16l+14)$	882
848	1	15	19	15	1	0	$4l+2, 5l\pm 2, 9^k(3l+2)$	900
849	5	7	8	2	0	5	$4l+2, 9l\pm 3, 25^k(5l\pm 1)$	900
850	1	7	36	0	0	1	$3l+2, 4l+2, 9l+3, 9^k(9l+6)$	972
851	5	8	9	-6	3	4	$3l+1, 4l+2, 9l+3, 9^k(9l+6)$	972
852	3	7	13	-3	1	2	$5l\pm 1, 8l+2, 16l+14, 25l\pm 5, 4^k(16l+6)$	1000
853	1	13	23	13	1	0	$4^k(16l+10), 9^k(9l+3), 169^k(13l+r) (r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11)$	1014
854	5	7	10	2	4	5	$23l+r (r = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 13, 16, 18), 4^k(16l+14)$	1058
855	3	9	11	3	3	0	$3l+1, 8l+6, 16l+10, 4^k(16l+2), 9^k(9l+6), 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	1080
856	6	7	10	7	3	6	$11l+r (r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9), 9^k(3l+2)$	1089
857*	1	10	29	5	1	0	$5l\pm 2, 9l\pm 3, 25^k(25l\pm 5)$	1125

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
858	2	7	22	-6	1	1	$5l \pm 1, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1125
859	5	6	11	3	5	0	$5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 10, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1125
860	5	9	9	9	3	3	$3l + 1, 9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 2)$	1134
861	5	5	13	1	1	3	$8l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1176
862	5	8	9	6	3	2	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1188
863	2	8	21	0	0	1	$3l + 1, 7l + r (r = 3, 5, 6), 9^k(9l + 6)$	1323
864	5	5	17	2	5	4	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1323
865	6	7	10	7	3	0	$3l + 2, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1323
866	1	19	19	8	1	1	$3l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 10)$	1350
867	5	9	11	9	5	0	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 10)$	1350
868	7	7	7	-1	1	1	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	1350
869	7	7	8	2	2	3	$4l + 2, 11l + r (r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9), 9^k(9l + 6)$	1452
870	7	7	8	-2	2	1	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 5, 9^k(9l + 3)$	1500
871	5	8	11	4	1	4	$3l + 1, 8l + 2, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	1512
872*	5	8	11	-4	1	2	$4l + 2, 9l + 3, 9^k(3l + 1)$	1620
873	8	9	9	9	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	1620
874	8	9	9	-3	6	6	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	1764
875	5	11	11	7	5	5	$8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	1800
876	7	7	13	2	7	4	$3l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	2025
877	5	10	13	10	1	2	$7l + r, (r = 1, 2, 4), 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	2058
878*	5	9	15	9	3	3	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 16l + 8, 9^k(9l + 3)$	2160
879	1	19	30	0	0	1	$5l \pm 2, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	2250
880	3	7	30	0	0	3	$5l \pm 1, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(3l + 2), 25^k(25l \pm 10)$	2250
881	9	9	11	9	9	3	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 5, 4^k(16l + 6)$	2250
882	9	9	11	3	6	9	$3l + 1, 9l + 3, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	2430
883	1	9	70	0	0	1	$4^k(16l + 14), 25^k(5l \pm 2), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 3, 5, 6)$	2450
884*	5	9	17	6	5	3	$3l + 1, 8l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 6, 32l + 8, 64l + 24, 4^k(16l + 14)$	2592
885	5	5	33	-3	3	4	$3l + 1, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	2646
886	6	7	19	7	6	0	$3l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(7l + r) (r = 1, 2, 4)$	2646
887	3	7	37	4	3	3	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 9^k(9l + 6)$	2700

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
888	3	17	17	8	3	3	$4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11$)	3042
889	7	10	13	5	1	4	$3l + 2, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $9^k(9l + 6)$	3267
890*	2	15	32	15	1	0	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 1, 25l \pm 5, 9^k(9l + 3)$	3375
891	8	11	11	1	4	4	$8l + 2, 16l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	3528
892	5	11	21	3	0	5	$9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 14), 9^k(3l + 1), 25^k(5l \pm 2)$	4050
893	7	13	13	-7	1	1	$4l + 2, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $9^k(3l + 2)$	4356
894	5	11	24	6	0	5	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 2, 25l \pm 10, 9^k(3l + 1)$	4500
895	7	8	23	6	7	2	$4l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	4500
896*	5	9	27	0	3	3	$3l + 1, 8l + 6, 9l \pm 3, 16l + 10, 4^k(16l + 2)$	4536
897	5	17	17	1	2	5	$3l + 1, 4l + 2, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	5292
898	7	13	19	8	7	7	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 9l + 3, 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	5292
899	7	7	28	-2	2	1	$3l + 2, 8l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	5400
900	11	11	15	3	3	8	$7l + r$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$), $4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(3l + 1), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	6174
901	3	17	35	5	0	3	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 1, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	6750
902	5	17	23	7	5	5	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(16l + 2)$	6750
903	7	13	22	2	4	7	$3l + 2, 5l \pm 1, 9l + 3, 25l \pm 10, 4^k(16l + 2)$	6750
904	9	11	21	3	9	6	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 2, 4^k(16l + 2), 9^k(9l + 6), 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	6750
905	5	17	26	2	4	5	$3l + 1, 7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $9l \pm 3, 4^k(16l + 14)$	7938
906	7	13	27	3	6	7	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	8100
907*	5	13	33	-6	3	1	$7l + r$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$), $8l + 2, 16l + 14, 4^k(16l + 6), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	8232
908	9	14	23	14	3	6	$3l + 1, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 169^k(13l + r)$ ($r = 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 11$)	9126
909*	9	11	29	-4	3	6	$3l + 1, 5l \pm 2, 9l \pm 3, 25^k(25l \pm 5)$	10125
910	5	17	33	9	3	2	$3l + 1, 8l + 6, 16l + 2, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 49^k(7l + r)$ ($r = 1, 2, 4$)	10584
911	7	13	37	13	1	2	$3l + 2, 9l + 6, 4^k(16l + 10), 9^k(9l + 3), 25^k(5l \pm 1)$	12150
912	7	13	39	-9	6	1	$3l + 2, 4l + 2, 11l + r$ ($r = 1, 3, 4, 5, 9$), $9^k(9l + 6)$	13068

Table 2: Positive integers not represented by odd regular primitive positive integral ternary quadratic forms $ax^2 + by^2 + cz^2 + dyz + ezx + fxy$								
no.	a	b	c	d	e	f	non-represented integers	disc.
913*	11	15	39	-3	6	3	$7l + r$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$), $8l + 6$, $16l + 10$, $4^k(16l + 2)$, $9^k(3l + 1)$, $49^k(49l + 7r)$ ($r = 3, 5, 6$)	24696

Table 3: Location of regular ternaries in the literature	
Reference	Ternaries
[6, p. 112]	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 12, 13, 16, 18, 20, 22, 23, 24, 31, 32, 33, 37, 39, 43, 45, 46, 52, 54, 61, 62, 63, 70, 71, 77, 81, 92, 94, 95, 105, 106, 108, 126, 130, 132, 133, 144, 146, 147, 163, 165, 176, 177, 178, 198, 200, 214, 217, 237, 238, 252, 255, 271, 288, 305, 315, 355
[6, p. 113]	26, 38, 72, 74, 85, 89, 96, 101, 104, 114, 115, 140, 148, 151, 181, 189, 190, 194, 205, 246, 247, 292, 311, 329, 330, 375, 378, 396, 419, 433, 437, 440, 445, 476, 490, 536, 565, 608
[9, p. 274]	1, 2, 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 16, 17, 18, 19, 29, 30, 37, 38
[9, p. 275]	4, 6, 12, 13, 14, 15, 22, 25, 26, 27
[8, p. 2]	2, 6
[3, p. 69]	8
[3, p. 70]	4
[11, p. 131]	4, 8, 11, 14, 15, 17, 19, 28
[5, p. 340]	7
[12, p. 110]	37, 38
[4, p. 40]	667, 671, 673, 716
[4, p. 42]	668, 695
[14, p. 173]	676
[1]	1
[15]	1
[7]	1
[2, p. 2082]	2,3,4,10
[2, p. 2083]	7,8,13,20